

Conductometric Study of Some Metal Complexes with Anthraquinone-1,8-disulphonic Acid

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In continuation of our work¹ on complexes of anthraquinone-1, 8-disulphonic acid (Na salt) with barium ion, a study of conductance of mixtures of anthraquinone-1,8-disulphonic acid (Na salt) and some metal salts (*vide infra*) has been undertaken, confirming the complex formation between Sr(II), Ca (II), and Pb (II) ions and anthraquinone-1,8-disulphonic acid (Na salt) in the ratio of 1:1. In every case, a yellow-coloured precipitate is formed which completely settles down overnight, leaving a clear supernatant liquid.

Standard solutions of the metal salts were prepared using AnalaR B.D.H. reagents [SrCl₂ · 6H₂O, CaCO₃ plus CH₃COOH, and Pb (NO₃)₂]. Anthraquinone-1, 8-disulphonic acid (Na salt) used was of L.R. B.D.H. quality. The experimental set-up and procedure were the same as in our previous communications¹⁻². The results are summarised in Table I. Here *c* represents the concentration of the metal solution and *p*, the ratio *c*'/*c* [*c*' being the concentration of anthraquinone-1, 8-disulphonic acid (Na salt) solution]. The total volume in each case was kept at 12 ml.

TABLE I

Salts.	<i>c</i> × 10 ⁻³ M.	<i>p</i> .	Fixed vol. of one component (ml).	Vol. at the peak or inflection (ml) metal.	Composition of the complex metal: anthraquinone-1, 8-disulphonic acid (Na salt).
A. By Job's method (equimol. and nonequimol. soln.).					
SrCl ₂	10.00	1.00	..	6.0	1:1
	6.66	1.00	..	6.0	1:1
	5.00	1.00	..	6.0	1:1
	13.33	0.50	..	4.0	1:1
	10.00	0.50	..	4.0	1:1
	5.00	2.00	..	8.0	1:1
Ca(Ao) ₂	13.33	1.00	..	6.0	1:1
	10.00	1.00	..	6.0	1:1
	5.00	1.00	..	6.0	1:1
	20.00	0.50	..	4.0	1:1
	10.00	0.50	..	4.0	1:1
	6.66	2.00	..	8.0	1:1

1. Joshi and Jain, *this Journal*, 1964, 41, 216.

2. *Idem, ibid.*, 1963, 40, 241, 242; 1964, 41, 33, 711.

TABLE I (contd.)

Salts.	$c \times 10^{-3}M.$	$p.$	Fixed vol. of one component (ml).	Vol. at the peak or inflection (ml) metal.	Composition of the complex metal: anthraquinone-1, 8-disulphonic acid (Na salt).
$Pb(NO_3)_2$	10.00	1.00	..	6.0	1 : 1
	6.66	1.00	..	6.0	1 : 1
	5.00	1.00	..	6.0	1 : 1
	10.00	0.50	..	4.0	1 : 1
	5.00	2.00	..	8.0	1 : 1
	3.33	2.00	..	8.0	1 : 1
B. By monovariation method (direct and reverse titrations).					
$NrCl_2$	13.33	1.00	4.0 each in direct and reverse titration	4.0 each in direct and reverse titration	1 : 1
$Ca(As)_2$ and $Pb(NO_3)_2$	10.00	1.00	Do	Do	1 : 1
	20.00	0.50	3.0 metal in direct titration	6.0 reagent in direct titration	1 : 1
			6.0 reagent in reverse titration	3.0 metal in reverse titration	1 : 1

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